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CULTURE OF ACADEMIC OPTIMISM VIS-À-VIS PERFORMANCE APPRAISAL: BOOSTING SCHOOL ACADEMIC BUOYANCY IN A CATHOLIC HEI

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Abstract

Catholic schools of Higher Educational Institutions (HEI) endeavor towards a culture of school academic optimism. The recent past global pandemic crisis impacted the world creating various approaches in the new educational landscape. This phenomenon affected the teaching-learning process specifically the schools' academic optimism in view of academic for both teacher and learner. Using a quantitative and correlational method, this study explored on the academic optimism of a Catholic HEI with full-time permanent tertiary faculty as respondents. This study intended to provide baseline information towards crafting mediatory activities to boost the school's academic optimism. This is significant to administrators, human resource development office, faculty and students to ensure academic achievements. Based on the results, the level of academic optimism of the school in three composite elements revealed a high level in collective efficacy, collective teacher trust in students and parents, and academic emphasis. The overall performance appraisal of the respondents varied from high to very high, while some opted not to indicate their rating. The control factors like sex, age, tenure, and highest educational attainment did not affect their academic optimism except on the school assignment and when compared across the composites which notd significant differences. There was significant correlation between faculty academic performance and academic optimism which implies that a high academic optimism affects the overall performance rating of the faculty, and vice-versa. The school's academic optimism is high but there are opportunities for improvement to sustain academic buoyancy. The academic optimism of the faculty must be enhanced specifically on collective faculty trust in faculty and parents, the lowest in the three domains. Thus, an enhancement activity must be conducted to sustain academic optimism and the schools' academic buoyancy.

Keywords: Collective Efficacy, Academic Achievement, Academic Emphasis, Faculty Trust, Academic Resilience, Catholic HEI

INTRODUCTION

Certainly, the school is significantly an important institution as part of every student's life for a certain duration of time in education. Like in any educational institution, the concern about school achievement becomes the current and actual concern, and the focus of attention not only of students but also teachers, parents, and all stakeholders. Of course, the student remains to be the most important of all concerns – the academic achievement of students.

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Šeboková & Uhláriková (2018) emphasize that the school is where the student acquires sufficient knowledge and develops individual skills and abilities especially through the school sense of belonging and integral formation and well-being. This means that the success of the student is intertwined with personality, self-confidence, emotions and overall behavior and survival. Some factors and variables may influence and increase students' achievement like teacher's personality, professional skills and abilities. In fact, the quality of teachers influences students, not just the teacher's professional degree, knowledge, and skills but also importantly their attitude toward teaching that if they trust their capacity to influence students' learning, they will be able to create greater expectations, develop more effort and they are more resilient in the case of educational or academic challenges. Seligman (2002) calls this as positive psychology which includes well-being, satisfaction, happiness, optimism, hope, belief, and zest for work which all involves subjectively positive experience.

Today, there is a need to increase the demands for greater academic achievement, hence, there is also a need to further explicate certain factors that positively influence students' performance and achievement. It is also noteworthy that there is continuous demand for academic achievement as education becomes more competitive. Beard, Hoy, & Woolfolk-Hoy (2009) believes that it is critical that researchers explore other areas in which schools can more positively influence academic success,

One specific concept that has emerged as a factor that can influence students' achievement is *academic optimism*. Developed by Wayne Hoy (2006b), academic optimism is a relatively new concept that uses Bandura's (1997) social cognitive and self-efficacy research as a theoretical foundation. Hoy explains academic optimism as an appropriate overarching construct to unite *efficacy, trust, and academic emphasis* because each concept contains a sense of the possible. Efficacy is the belief that the teacher can make a positive difference in student learning; teachers believe in themselves. Teachers trust in students and parents is the belief that teachers, parents, and students cooperate to improve learning, that is, the faculty believes in its students. Academic emphasis is the enacted behavior prompted by these beliefs, that is, the focus is student success. Thus, a school with high academic optimism enables the faculty to believe they can make a difference, trust that students can learn, and academic performance can be achieved. The three components of *academic emphasis, faculty trust, and collective efficacy* interact together and influence the overall culture and climate of the school.

In this study, the researcher focused on the school's academic optimism as a significant factor that may predict and influence the academic achievement of a student. Although throughout time the specific goals of education have changed, based on community needs of the period, the ultimate goals of education have always been to increase one's knowledge, prepare individuals to lead more productive lives, and to encourage contributions to the greater good in an ever-changing society. There are no substitutes for a high-quality education, as its effects can span for generations. As educational institutions continue to seek to increase educational attainment and increase students' achievement, it is critical in this post-pandemic era to focus intently on the state of school's academic optimism in view of the academic achievement of students in the midst of the multi-faceted challenges of education in its new learning modalities.

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In fact, Beard & Hoy (2009) claim that academic optimism is a factor that influences academic achievement and in three components, namely, collective efficacy, academic emphasis, and faculty trust in parents and students (Hoy, Tarter, & Woolfolk-Hoy, 2006). They assert that the true goals of education are to prepare individuals to lead more productive lives and contribute to the greater good in an ever-changing society. In fact, education has been acknowledged as being the driving force behind successful organizations, communities, and nations (Hewitt, 2008).

Hence, as schools indispensably consider academic achievement of students, it is imperative to determine some contributory factors that are both related to and influence the academic optimism of schools. As educational leaders and teachers continue to be responsible for academic growth of students, there is a necessity to adequately identify those factors to increase acquisition of knowledge within the educational systems especially in today's post-pandemic times. The studies of Bryk (2010); Burney & Beilke (2008); and Nettles & Herrington (2007), attest that there are existing number of research on low performing schools and yet there are still so many schools that are not meeting the academic needs of students. Thus, this recurring challenging phenomenon suggests that other factors need to be explored.

It is in this context that this research was conducted. Catholic schools of HEIs must exerting efforts in search for possibilities and opportunities to sustain its culture of academic optimism in view of its optimum service in enhancing students' academic achievement. Although the construct of academic optimism is relatively new, emerging research and related studies Focusing on the elements of academic optimism of both teachers and administrators of a school for this study can possibly provide insight for educational leaders.

Hence, this study on academic optimism is an immediate, timely and greatly relevant in this time of post-pandemic experiences. More so, studies on academic optimism are rather scanty in the Philippine educational setting, thus, this research. As academic optimism endeavors to contribute to the creation of a climate and culture in which student achievement is prioritized, the teachers, administrators, parents, and most importantly the students who are the primary beneficiaries of this study. Moreover, this study is vital for future researchers as they continuously search and explore for knowledge and wisdom in helping establish academic excellence through the school's academic optimism.

Conceptual Analytical Framework

This study is founded on some relevant concepts, principles, theories and other related body of knowledge that are contributory to academic optimism and its underlying predictors or domains. The theory of academic optimism was initially introduced Hoy (2018) using three streams of research over several decades. He converged three significant predictors in his studies, namely, *collective efficacy*, *collective faculty trust*, and *academic emphasis*. Results of his study affirm that these three domains have consistently been positively associated with academic achievement of students. These three elements and their interactions create the construct of academic optimism.. *Collective efficacy* is the belief that the faculty can make a positive contribution to student learning. *Faculty trust* in parents and

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students implies that parents, teachers, and students can cooperate to improve learning. *Academic emphasis* is the enacted behavior driven by efficacy and trust beliefs, all of which focus on academic success of students. These three collective and interconnected concepts work in a unified fashion to create a theory of academic optimism. Hoy (2018) *defines academic optimism* as a collective set of beliefs about the strengths and capabilities of a school in which optimism is the overarching theme that unifies collective efficacy and collective trust with academic emphasis. A robust culture of academic optimism functions to improve the academic performance in schools by providing the school with a strong motivational structure that focuses on academic achievement.

Collective Efficacy is the shared perceptions of teachers in a school that efforts of the school in general will have a positive effect on students (Hoy & Miskel, 2013). It is the belief of one individual that the entire school faculty could positively affect academic achievement. The basis of collective efficacy is personal of self-efficacy. According to self-efficacy theory, both children and adults develop certain beliefs about their ability to accomplish specific tasks (Grusec, 1992). Goddard & Skrla (2006) note, "The stronger an organization's collective efficacy beliefs, the more likely that its members are to put forth the sustained effort and persistence required to attain desired goal." An individual's behavior is, based on his or her beliefs. Erdem and Demirel (2007) affirm that self-efficacy is a belief that has an immense impact on one's sense of responsibility and actions.

Collective faculty trust in students and parents is the willingness of the teacher and the school to risk vulnerability to a parents and colleagues with confidence that both groups can be relied upon, i.e., are benevolent, competent, and open. It is the extent to which the teacher trust that both students and parents will contribute to the goals of high academic excellence. This refers to the levels of trust that the faculty has for its students and teachers that they will work together toward the educational goals of academic achievement.

Academic emphasis is the school's aim for academic achievement. A school with high academic emphasis has high achievement standards. This includes a belief that all students can achieve, in an environment conducive to learning with high expectations of students, and recognition of academic excellence. Academic emphasis sets high but achievable academic goals are set for students where the learning environment is orderly and serious; students are motivated to work hard; and students respect academic achievement (Hoy, Tarter, & Woolfolk Hoy, 2006).

Bandura's (1997) social cognitive theory affirm that the more one experiences success, it builds their confidence that they can continue being successful. In relation to academic emphasis of a school, as the school experiences success, whether determined by state accountability measures or other methods, they are more likely to continue increasing academic emphasis. In fact, studies reveal that academic emphasis does directly and positively influence student achievement (Beard et al., 2009; Goddard et al., 2000; Hoy et al., 2006c). Such studies firmly attest that academic emphasis has a positive effect on students' performance. Schools with a culture of academic excellence are fostered by their goals in academic emphasis. Hence, academic emphasis determines that teachers and students are consistently engaged in effective practices and strategies that foster teaching and learning.

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Academic buoyancy is a construct reflecting everyday academic optimism within a positive psychology context. Martin, A. J. & Marsh, Herbert (2008) define academic buoyancy as the ability to successfully deal with academic setbacks and challenges that are typical of the ordinary course of school life. Some of these include low grades, competing deadlines, examination pressure, and difficult schoolwork.

Based on these principles and concepts, this study indicates the relations between and among the foregoing variables as manifested in the research paradigm as shown below:

The Research Paradigm

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As reflected in the paradigm, this study focused on the academic buoyancy of a university vis-a-vis the academic optimism faculty respondents initially through their profile which included sex, age, tenure (length of service or number of years of teaching [actual years]), and highest educational attainment, and school assignment. It determined the level of academic optimism three composite elements, namely, collective efficacy, collective teacher trust in students and parents, and academic emphasis. The level of academic optimism was compared with the overall performance appraisal respondents for AY 2021-2022. Based the item indicators, it determines emerging challenges in the three identified domains. Based on the results, it provided baseline information as basis of an intervention activities to enhance the level of academic optimism of the university. Specifically, this study answered the following problems:

1. What is the level of the schools' academic optimism as perceived by the faculty-respondents in following composite elements:
 - a. Collective Efficacy
 - b. Collective Faculty Trust in Faculty and Parents
 - c. Academic Emphasis
2. What is the overall performance rating of the faculty-respondents for the Academic Year 2021-2022?
3. Is there significant difference on level of academic optimism of the faculty-respondents when grouped according to their profiles?
4. Is there a significant difference on the level of academic optimism when compared across the three composite elements?
5. Is there significant correlation between the level of academic optimism and the level of performance rating of the faculty-respondents?
6. What emerging challenges do they encounter in their academic optimism and what are their recommendations to enhance academic optimism the faculty?
7. What school-based mediatory activities or programs can be crafted and proposed to enhance the schools' academic optimism?

Based on these problems, this study postulated that there is no significant difference on the level of academic optimism of the teacher-respondents when grouped according to profile variables; no significant difference on the level of academic optimism when compared across the three composite elements; and no correlation between the level of academic optimism and the level of the overall performance rating of the faculty respondents.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

Utilizing a quantitative or descriptive and correlational method method, the current used survey technique. The descriptive part includes information on the faculty-respondents

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profile such as sex, age, tenure (length of service or years teaching), highest educational attainment, school assignment and performance rating (AY 2021-2022).

The level of academic optimism was determined in three major predictors or domains, namely, the collective efficacy, faculty's trust on students and parents, and academic emphasis. Using open-ended questions, it determined the emerging challenges encountered by the faculty respondents as well as their vital recommendations to boost their academic optimism. It compared the level of academic optimism of faculty respondents on the three composite elements with the respondents' profile and across the three domains or composite elements. Moreover, it determined the correlation of the level of academic optimism and the level of overall appraisal rating of the faculty respondents. Based on the vital findings, an activity was crafted to enhance the school's academic optimism among faculty members of SMU tertiary level.

This study was conducted at St. Mary University – Philippines, an HEI Tertiary Department. The department is composed of four undergraduate departments, namely, School of Accountancy and Business, School of Engineering, Architecture, and Information Technology, School of Health and Natural Sciences, and the School of Accountancy and Business. This population study was able to retrieve a total of 88 out of 115 tertiary full time permanent faculty members for the Academic Year 2022-2023 (Second Semester). These respondents were selected based on their tenure and experiences in teaching in the university.

To gather the needed data, transmittal letters were addressed to seek permission to conduct the study to the heads of offices of the faculty respondents. A separate transmittal letter was addressed to the respondents to seek permission through an Informed Consent Form. The survey commenced immediately after the approval was sought. Eventually, the survey will be retrieved. The data were tabulated using the spreadsheet and then transformed to the IBM Statistical Packages for the Social Sciences (SPSS) Statistics for treatment using appropriate tools. Because of the non-normal distribution of the respondents, non-parametric tools were used. The survey used a 5-point Likert scale (1.0-5.0) from strongly disagree to strongly agree. The level of academic optimism of schools in the three composites were determined through computation of mean scores, weighted mean scores and standard deviations

For the inferential aspect, Mann-Whitney U for two categorical variables and or Kruskal-Wallis for three or more categorical variables tests were used. Friedman test was used in the correlation. Lastly, an activity to enhance the academic optimism of the schools was crafted based on the salient findings of this study focusing on the emerging challenges of the faculty respondents.

For ethical consideration, *this* study was submitted to the school for ethics review. There was no conflict of interest in this study as the current researchers are part of the study population. There is no financial gain expected by the researchers as this study primarily intends to contribute to the benefit of the school and in the field of future research along this line. All the gathered information and all related data were treated with sanctity and full confidentiality. The data gathering was administered exclusively by the researchers after explaining the parameters, goals and objectives of the research accompanied by a consent

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form. There were no foreseen risks in this study affecting health aspects or financial matters/financial compensation or gain that may affect or influence the participation of the respondents. The intellectual property rights on the results of this study are owned and accorded to the researchers and the school as provider of research honorarium. Moreover, the survey tool with high reliability alpha coefficient is adapted as utilized in the study of LaQuanta Murray Nelson (2012) initially conceptualized by Hoy, W. K., Tarter, C. J., & Woolfolk Hoy, A. (2006)

RESULTS

There was a total of 88 respondents dominated by male (64.8%) as against the female (35.2%). Most respondents were with masteral and doctoral units (50%), with masteral and doctoral degrees (35.2%) and bachelor’s degree (14.8%). Most of the respondents came from the School of teacher Education and Humanities (44.3%), School of Health and Natural Sciences (20.5%), School of Accountancy and Business (18.2%), and school of Engineering, Architecture and Information Technology (17.2%). The age gap of the respondents was relatively closed where most of them ranged from 29-39 (36.4%), 40-46 (33.0%), and above 47 (30.7%). By length of service, most of them served above 19 years (38.6%), 11-18 (31.8%), and 5-50 (29.5%).

The level of the school’s academic optimism in the three composite elements are presented in the table below, namely, collective efficacy, faculty trust to students and faculty, and academic emphasis.

The Level of School’s Academic Optimism in Three Composites

	Mean	Std. Deviation	QD
A. COLLECTIVE EFFICACY			
1. Teachers in this school can get through to the most difficult students.	3.99	.766	H
2. Teachers here are confident they will be able to motivate their students.	4.36	.529	H
3. If a student doesn’t want to learn, teachers here do not give up.	4.17	.776	H
4. Teachers here have the skills needed to produce meaningful results.	4.45	.585	H
5. Teachers in this school believe that every child can learn.	4.74	.442	VH
6. These students come to school ready to learn	3.73	1.19	H
7. Home life provide so many advantages that students are bound to learn.	3.97	.877	H
8. Students in this school are motivated to learn.	3.98	.625	H
9. Teachers in this school do have the skills to deal with students’ disciplinary problems.	4.06	.650	H
10. The opportunities in this community help ensure that these students will learn.	4.45	.501	H
11. Learning is easier at this school because students are not worried about their safety.	4.31	.849	H
12. This community is drug-free and alcohol-free that make learning convenient for students.	4.44	.544	H

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Total Mean	4.22	.36961	H
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B. COLLECTIVE FACULTY TRUST IN STUDENTS AND PARENTS

1. Teachers in this school trust their students	3.80	.406	H
2. Teachers in this school trust the parents.	3.82	.388	H
3. Students in this school care about each other.	3.65	.712	H
4. Parents in this school are reliable in their commitments.	3.80	.406	H
5. Students in this school can be counted upon to do their work.	3.77	.421	H
6. Teachers can count on parental support.	3.83	.378	H
7. Teachers here believe that students are competent students.	3.82	.492	H
8. Teachers think that most of the parents do a good job	3.77	.421	H
9. Teachers can believe what parents tell them.	3.75	.435	H
10. Students here are not secretive.	3.33	.690	H
Total Mean	3.73	.26467	H

C. ACADEMIC EMPHASIS

1. The school sets high standards for performance.	4.55	.896	VH
2. Students respect others who get good grades.	4.13	.842	H
3. Students seek extra work/activities so they can get good grades.	3.94	.701	H
4. Academic achievement is recognized and acknowledged by the school.	4.85	.357	VH
5. Students try hard to improve on previous work.	4.01	.616	H
6. The learning environment here is orderly and friendly.	4.49	.547	H
7. The students in this school can achieve the goals that have been set for them	4.19	.544	H
8. Teachers in this school believe that their students have the ability to achieve academically	4.49	.503	H
Total Mean	4.33	.41053	H

Overall Mean	4.09	.27613	H
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Legend: 1:00-1.49=Strongly Disagree/Very Low; 1.50-2.49=Disagree/Low; 2.50-3.49=Somewhat Agree/Moderate; 3.50-4.49=Agree/High; and 4.50-5:00=Strongly Agree/Very Highly

Based on the results, the overall level of the school's academic optimism is high in the three composites such as collective efficacy, trust of faculty to students and parents, and academic emphasis.

Rated highest in the three domains is *academic emphasis*. The respondents agreed that the school sets high standards for performance and students respect others with good grades like those who seek extra activities. Th faculty highly agreed that students try to improve their performance because the learning environment is orderly and friendly. In fact, the faculty highly agreed that students in this school can achieve their goals with their ability to achieve academically. Notable in this domain is the recognition and acknowledgement given by the school to students which was rated very high by the respondents.

Collective efficacy was rated high. The faculty-respondents agree to a high extent that teachers in this school can handle the most difficult students and they can motivate them to achieve without giving up on them; teachers possess the necessary skills to produce meaningful results; and they strongly believe, to a very great extent, that every student can learn. They also highly agree that students come to school ready as their home provide many advantages to learn because they are motivated to learn in school. They also highly trust that

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opportunities in the community ensure easier learning because the students do not worry about their safety in school that is drug and alcohol free which makes learning convenient for them.

Notably, the lowest composite based on the mean scores in almost all item indicators is the *faculty trust on students and parents*, though it is still classified as high. The respondents modestly agree that teachers in this school trust the students and parents and in the way they manifest care about each other. They fairly agree that parents are reliable in their commitments and parental support. Even students were fairly counted upon in doing their work. The respondents fairly agree that students are competent and are not secretive. They also modestly agreed that parents are doing well their job and believe what parents tell them.

Regarding the overall performance rating of the respondent, results reveal that 58.0% were rated very satisfactory (high), and 23.9% outstanding (very high) while 18.2% refused to indicate their overall performance rating. In short, out of the 88 respondents, 51 were very satisfactory, 21 were outstanding and 16 did not indicate their rating. The comparisons reveal that the control factors like sex, age, tenure, and highest educational attainment did not affect their academic optimism except on the school assignment at .050 on academic emphasis and when compared across the composites which noted significant differences at .000. Moreover, there was significant correlation between faculty academic performance and academic optimism at .005.

One of the notable challenges to the faculty is on the aspect of trust to students and parents. With the emerging demands of the educational system regarding the academic achievement of students and the role of parents in the new normal, the respondents find it challenging to establish trust in ensuring competence while seemingly doubting whether students even care about each other as well as whether they count of the support of parents to them. In fact, students have the tendency to be secretive. They also fairly believe whether the parents are doing well in their assistance to the students. Hence, they could hardly rely on parental support as well as the students' self-determination in their academic endeavors. Moreover, they recommend that a stronger collaboration must be forged between the faculty and students, including their parents to further enhance the school's academic optimism. With these results, an activity was crafted to boost the academic optimism of the school to sustain its academic buoyancy dubbed as "Taripnong: Reinforcing Collective Academic Trust via Strengthened School-Home Alliance."

Discussions

This study affirms the importance of schools' academic optimism to sustain its academic buoyancy in view of students' academic achievement. The role of the faculty is crucial. The results could affirm Šeboková & Uhláriková (2018) who claim that the school provides the student with sufficient knowledge and develops individual skills and abilities especially through the school sense of belonging and integral formation and well-being. This becomes possible through the school's academic optimism. With a considerably high academic optimism, the success of the student becomes intertwined good personality and character as well as self-confidence, emotions and overall behavior and survival, thus academically buoyant. Several factors.

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Collective efficacy is an important factor may influence and increase students' achievement. Seligman (2002) calls this as positive psychology which includes well-being, satisfaction, happiness, optimism, hope, belief, and zest for work which all involves subjectively positive experience. With collective efficacy, teachers will be able to reach out to the most difficult students with the needed confidence to motivate them without giving up even when students refuse to learn. Teachers become upskilled to produce meaningful outcomes in student learnings. Collective efficacy enables the teacher to believe that every student can learn and become ready to learn when they come to school because they are motivated by the teachers. With this disposition, teachers will be ready to deal with students' disciplinary issues especially when the school community provides opportunities to help ensure that students will learn. With high collective efficacy learning becomes easier because students are ensured of their safety in a clean, healthy, safe and friendly environment. This is the contention of Beard, Hoy, & Woolfolk-Hoy (2009) that it is critical to explore other areas in which schools can more positively influence academic success for students. Hence, collective efficacy necessarily includes the personality, professional skills and abilities of the faculty because the quality of teachers influences students, not only to the teacher's professional degree, knowledge and skills but also to their attitude toward teaching. This means that teachers who believe their capacity to influence students' learning, will eventually create higher expectations, develop more effort and they become more resilient any educational or academic challenges. This study coincides with the claim of Hoy & Miskel, (2013) that collective efficacy establishes the belief that the school has the ability to positively affect academic achievement where the teacher has the ability to find opportunities to increase student achievement. In fact, Goddard & Skrla (2006) affirm that "the stronger an organization's collective efficacy beliefs, the more likely that its members are to put forth the sustained effort and persistence required to attain desired goal." Erdem and Demirel (2007) share a similar contention claiming that self-efficacy can be considered a belief that has an immense impact on one's sense of responsibility and actions.

This study attests that collective trust of teachers to students and their parents is a key factor in academic optimism. A high collective trust ensures the teachers' confidence to the competence of their students and rely on the commitment of parents and their parental support. It is therefore important that trust is forged between the teachers and students including their parents in the true sense of collaboration or alliance in pursuit of the academic achievement of the students. A high collective trust enables teachers, students, and parents to ensures the realization of the goals for high academic excellence though collaboration. Hence, this study supports Hoy, Tarter, and Woolfolk-Hoy (2006) that trusting others is a fundamental aspect of human learning because learning is typically a cooperative process, and distrust makes cooperation virtually impossible. Thus, when students, teachers, and parents have a common learning goal, trust and cooperation, teaching and learning will be improved. Moreover, this study also affirms Tschannen-Moran (2004) emphasizing that trust both binds organizational participants together and assists the organization in running smoothly involving the entire school setting such as the students, teachers, administrators, and parents.

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This study attests that high academic emphasis ensures a school with high achievement standards especially when teachers believe that all students can achieve in an environment where they work hard and respect those who achieve.

Academic emphasis focusses on environments that are conducive to learning, with high expectations on students, and recognizes academic excellence. High academic emphasis drives the school towards a quest for academic excellence and academic achievement. This study corresponds to Hoy, Tarter, & Woolfolk Hoy (2006) claiming that high but achievable academic goals are vital for students; ensures the and orderly learning environment where students are motivated to work hard; and respect academic achievement. Furthermore, this study also affirms Beard et al. (2009); Goddard et al. (2000); Hoy et al. (2006) that academic emphasis directly and positively influence students' achievement. In fact, schools with a culture of academic excellence are advanced in academic emphasis teachers and students become consistently engaged in effective practices and strategies in the teaching learning process.

Hence, the culture of academic optimism must continue to sustain academic buoyancy in all Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) among faculty regardless of sex, age, educational attainment, tenure, or school assignment. However, the performance of teachers could affect their level of academic optimism, or vice-versa. The schools' academic buoyancy as attested by Martin, A. J. & Marsh, Herbert (2008) reflects the everyday academic optimism in responding to academic setbacks and challenges of the ever-dynamic educational landscape.

However, this study recognizes its limitation as it focuses mainly on the experiences of the faculty including their overall performance which is more of a self-survey that is primarily an initial preliminary study. As discussed in this study, academic optimism necessarily includes students as it is mainly geared towards their academic achievement. Hence, further research may focus on student experiences to affirm, negate or enhance the findings of this study.

Conclusion

Based on the results of the study, some conclusions can be drawn. First, the overall academic optimism of the school is highly laudable in all three composites with different levels from highest to lowest, namely, academic emphasis, collective efficacy, collective faculty trust to students and parents, respectively. Similarly, the overall performance rating is commendable as they manifest very satisfactory and outstanding performance, though some opted not to indicate their ratings. The academic optimism of the school was not influenced by profiles such as sex, age, tenure, and highest educational attainment except when compared by schools and across the three composites. However, academic optimism and academic performance are intertwined which implies that the higher the teachers' performance and so thus the school's academic optimism, and/or vice-versa. One important challenge that needs to be addressed is the collective trust to students and parents. In an ever-changing and challenging demands of the educational system in the new educational

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landscape, it is important to forge a stronger alliance and meaningful collaboration of teachers, students, and parents in ensuring the need academic optimism to sustain the school's academic buoyancy. Thus, to address this need, an activity to enhance academic optimism was crafted and proposed.

Recommendations

Based on the results and findings this study highly recommends that academic optimism including collective efficacy, collective faculty trust to students and parents, and academic emphasis must be enhanced to sustain the schools' academic buoyancy to ensure academic achievement among students especially in the dynamically changing educational landscapes brought about by current trends and challenges as well as the academic demands of new platforms of the teaching-learning process. As attested in this study, collective trust among teachers, students, and parents are necessary to ensure students' academic achievement through stronger alliance and meaningful collaborations. Thus, an activity must be conducted to sustain and enhance the trust of faculty to students and the role parents should contribute with commitment.

The role of the faculty is crucial in academic optimism. Thus, the teacher's overall academic performance must be sustained as it has significant connection with academic optimism. Institutional programs must be sustained to ensure their optimum work performances and academic endeavors. More timely than ever, academic buoyancy should be a necessary aspect of a culture of academic optimism that schools must establish and sustain in the current times.

This study is basically a preliminary self-survey of faculty. It is recommended that research of this nature be conducted to students including their academic performances.

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